

Original papers

Addressing multidimensional highly correlated data for forecasting in precision beekeeping

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, there have been relevant advances in precision beekeeping. These advances are mainly focused on proposing sensor systems that collect crucial information for bee welfare, creating integrated architectures that allow beekeepers to monitor the current state of their hive through real-time data. However, there is a lack of predictive models that would allow beekeepers to anticipate specific events that endanger bee welfare and lead to a decline in productivity. Specifically, predictive approaches accounting for the high correlation among internal variables of beehives have not been developed to date. To address this research gap, multivariate predictive models, including auto-regressive state-space and time series models, have been implemented and applied to four different hives from the we4bee project. These models aim to predict the internal variables of beehives (four different temperatures, humidity, and weight) by utilizing the meteorological conditions to which the hives are exposed. A cross-validation adapted to time series data was employed for model generalization assessment. Prediction models based on vector time series exhibited superior performance in forecasting internal hive variables compared to multivariate auto-regressive state-space models. Overall, the approach based on the vector error correction model yielded the best balance between fit, prediction, and computational cost. The VEC-based approach produces predictions with maximum mean absolute errors of 177 (312)g in weight, 3.366 (3.802)% in humidity, and 1.122 (1.685)°C in temperature at 1 (3)-days ahead when dealing with beehives exhibiting a high degree of correlation in their internal variables. Moreover, the VEC-based approach requires less than a second to perform the time series fitting process, which makes it particularly interesting for application in big data environments. The integration of such models into a decision support system would meet the need of beekeepers to anticipate potential threats to the welfare of their bee colonies, streamlining their monitoring processes while eliminating the need for continuous inspections.

1. Introduction

Beekeeping is essential for preserving and improving the health of ecosystems, facilitating plant propagation and increasing agricultural production, thus ensuring the balance and optimal functioning of natural systems (Ghosh et al., 2020). Moreover, due to bees' sensitivity to environmental changes, they can be used as biosensors providing essential information to detect pollutants or alterations in climate (Zahid Sharif et al., 2021).

In recent years, a significant decline in the bee population has been observed, primarily linked to the loss of their natural habitat (Lima et al., 2022), the use of pesticides (Tosi et al., 2022), and the repercussions of climate change (Albacete et al., 2023). The reduction in bee populations is a problem of worldwide importance, highlighted

by the several initiatives undertaken by different governments and international entities for the conservation of bees (Schatz et al., 2021).

Precision beekeeping represents a remarkable technological advance for this sector, enabling more effective and precise hive management for beekeepers through the integration of innovative technologies (Zacepins et al., 2015). This multidisciplinary approach incorporates the use of sensors, geographic information systems, data analytics, and other state-of-the-art technologies to compile detailed information on bee behavior, health conditions, and the surrounding environmental factors (Hadjur et al., 2022).

Research on precision beekeeping is receiving a great attention as the number of research articles and reviews are increasing (Alleri et al., 2023). Most of these studies focus on the development of sensor-based systems to monitor the status of hives in real time that collect

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information on parameters which directly influence bee health (Danieli et al., 2024). The parameters of greatest interest include temperature, which provides indications of swarm events (Zacepins et al., 2016) or the potential for disease proliferation (Dalmon et al., 2019); the weight of the hive, which is directly related to important events occurring in the hive, such as the start of nectar collection, resource consumption, the need to include food or the state of health, among others (Kviesis et al., 2020; Degenfellner and Templ, 2024); and the relative humidity, which, when combined with other variables such as temperature or carbon dioxide concentration, provides information about the health status of the hive (Bencsik et al., 2023). The sound emitted by the bees (Truong et al., 2023), vibration spectrum (Ramsey et al., 2020), air quality (Szcurek et al., 2020) and video recordings (Voudiotis et al., 2021) are other considered measurements.

Despite the advances introduced by precision beekeeping in apiary management and administration, beekeeping is still a field in which traditional hive management predominate over the incorporation of new technology. One of the problems that arises in this context is the fact that, when handling sensor databases, the quality is highly determined by the sensor system's integrity and correct functionality. Sensor failures introduce inaccuracies, missing data, and, in some cases, complete periods of data absence, which entails working with databases that are challenging to address. Since the effective training of any predictive model is highly dependent on the quantity and accuracy of data, this problem results in a scarce availability of predictive models that allow beekeepers to discern hive dynamics, which would allow them to mitigate possible events that could have a significant economic impact, such as susceptibility to diseases, swarming events or colony mortality, among other.

To date, research focusing on predicting the internal conditions of beehives based on data provided by sensors remains notably limited. Braga et al. (2021) used a long short-term memory (LSTM) neural network algorithm to predict temperature drops in the hive by using the internal humidity, average ventilation, average hive noise, and external temperature of the hive. Robustillo et al. (2022) focused on comparing multivariate predictive algorithms to predict internal conditions of relative humidity, temperature, and hive weight in bee colonies incorporating information regarding the meteorological conditions to which the beehive is exposed. Anwar et al. (2022) uses random forest regression to estimate daily hive weight change by using internal hive variables such as temperature, humidity, atmospheric pressure, CO₂ levels, acoustic variables, vibrations and hive weight, together with various external meteorological variables. These results were subsequently enhanced by Anwar et al. (2023), who proposed an hybrid deep learning model for soft detection and time series forecasting to estimate the daily weight variations of beehives. Finally, Rigakis et al. (2023) used an additive regression model and the extreme gradient machine learning algorithm (XGboost) for regression to predict the internal humidity of beehives incorporating additional variables such as temperature, weight, CO₂ concentration, bee entrances and exits, hive vibration and total concentration of volatile organic compounds. Upon comparison, it was observed that the additive regression model yielded more stable results, attributing this stability to the pronounced overfitting exhibited by the XGBoost model.

The limited number of studies on prediction of hive conditions highlights the need to move in this direction in order to expand the benefits of precision beekeeping for beekeepers, making it more compelling. There is a research gap in the implementation and development of multivariate models for predicting internal variables in beehives. Specifically, to the best of the authors' knowledge, no research article has yet focused on the prediction of highly correlated internal variables in beehives. This article aims to address this research gap in the context of precision beekeeping by presenting suitable statistical models that solve the issue of predicting multiple highly correlated variables associated with the internal conditions of bee hives.

In this article, predictive models are implemented and compared to predict highly correlated variables, allowing the incorporation of multiple measurements of the same response variable at different locations across Germany. The aim of this work is to predict internal temperature in four different points of the hive as well as the relative humidity and weight. For this purpose, six endogenous variables and different exogenous variables, measuring the climatic conditions to which the hive is exposed, are considered. Four beehives from the we4bee project (<https://we4bee.org/>) are considered to collect sensor data, which were properly preprocessed. Firstly, a search for erroneous values (attributed to sensor failures) was conducted, leading to their removal. Subsequently, these eliminated values, along with the remaining missing values, were imputed. Five models consistent with the experimental design based on highly correlated data were implemented, applied and compared. To assess the stability and predictive accuracy of the models, a time series-adapted cross-validation process was undertaken. Predictions have been made at 1- and 3-days ahead, enough time for the beekeeper to anticipate and act on events that may occur and endanger the hive health. For instance, temperature and humidity predictions can help anticipate favorable conditions for the development of certain diseases, such as varroa. The optimal reproduction rate of varroa occurs at temperatures between 32.5 °C and 34.5 °C, combined with relative humidity ranges between 55% and 70% (Nazzi and Le Conte, 2016). An additional example of applying hive temperature and weight predictions is the early detection of queen loss. According to Lu et al. (2024), queen loss has a significant impact on both the hive's temperature and weight. Early detection of queen loss can alert beekeepers to introduce a new queen, thereby preserving the hive's reproductive capacity.

The rest of this article is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the databases used. Section 3 presents the predictive models considered as well as the methodology used to compare them. Section 4 shows the obtained results, and in Section 5 a discussion is presented. Finally, Section 6 presents the conclusions.

2. Data description

The we4bee project collects sensor data from hives, mostly located at Germany and makes them accessible through its website (<https://we4bee.org/>). This project placed Kenya top bar hives mainly at schools and educational institutions, aiming to promote awareness regarding bees and their crucial role in the ecosystem. The primary objective of this hive variant is not honey extraction, but rather concentrating on the minimally invasive maintenance of bees, thereby aiming for the least disruptive and most natural possible approach.

Information gathered by the sensors includes details about both the internal conditions: four different measurements of temperature (°C), relative humidity (%), and weight (kg) and the meteorological conditions affecting the beehive: temperature, humidity, rainfall (ml), wind speed (m/s), air pressure (hPa), particulate matter (µg/m³) discriminating between small and larger size particles, and brightness (lx). The data from all sensors were recorded five times a day at evenly spaced time intervals. The placement of different sensors in the beehives of this project is illustrated in Fig. 1. Specifically, A represents the entrance hole, while B, C, and D are sensors measuring temperature at different locations within the hive. Sensor E measures internal temperature and relative humidity, F is a scale recording weight, and G houses sensors responsible for registering meteorological conditions.

Despite the presence of many beehives in the project, most of them do not provide sufficiently lengthy historical data series because we consider series with at least one year and seven months of information. It is important to emphasize that collecting data over extended periods, particularly those exceeding two years, presents a significant challenge within the field of precision apiculture. Many instances exhibit extended periods devoid of data collection, rendering them unsuitable for analysis. Consequently, data from four distinct beehives have been

Fig. 1. Representation of sensor located at a we4bee project's hive. A represents the entrance hole, B, C, and D are temperature (°C) sensors, E is a sensor registering both temperature (°C) and humidity (%), F is the scale measuring the weight (kg), and sensors dedicated to recording climatological conditions are located at position G.

Fig. 2. Geographic representation of Germany with the placement of the researched beehives. Hagen and Waltrap are in the state of North Rhine-Westphalia and Vohburg an der Donau and Ingolstadt in the Bavarian region.

gathered. Specifically, the Ingolstadt's hive database collects information from December 9, 2019 to August 25, 2021, the Hagen's hive presents information from July 1, 2020 to February 28, 2022, the Vohburg an der Donau's hive recorded information from July 17, 2019 to April 7, 2021, and finally, the Waltrap's hive contains information from May 1, 2020 to February 21, 2022. Fig. 2 presents the location of the hives.

After obtaining each database, the challenge emerges of handling imperfect data marked by missing values and incorrect data attributed to sensor failures. To address this situation, a search for invalid data was performed. Measurement errors were recognized to occur when the measurements deviated beyond a plausible range. These values were deemed indicative of sensor failures and consequently excluded, becoming new missing data. Specifically, instances were identified when the internal temperature exceeded 43 °C, humidity surpassed

Table 1

Overview of the imputation percentages across each beehive database, categorizing imputation cases into out-of-range values, meteorological data from neighboring beehives, and other missing values unrelated to these groups. Finally, the overall percentage of imputed data is presented.

	Hagen	Ingolstadt	Vohburg	Waltrap
Out of range (%)	1.58	0.00	0.00	2.26
Nearby hive (%)	0.00	3.33	0.80	1.99
Other missing data (%)	3.47	3.32	1.02	1.49
Total (%)	5.05	6.65	1.82	5.74

100% or fell below 0%, weight descended below 0 kg, rainfall measured less than 0 ml or exceeded 1 ml (maximum amount detected by the sensor), wind speed fell below 0 m/s, or air pressure dropped below 0 hPa. Besides these exclusions certain beehives experienced time intervals in which sensor data were not recorded. To efficiently apply the imputation method, meteorological information obtained from a nearby beehive was introduced. Table 1 illustrates the percentage of imputed data in each database. To enhance comprehension of data quality, distinctions are made among the percentages of out-of-range data, data containing information on the meteorological conditions of nearby beehives (indicating periods when sensors did not register information for any variable), the percentage of other missing data, unrelated to the previously mentioned cases, and, lastly, the total percentage of imputed data for each database.

Missing data were imputed by using the Multivariate Imputation by Chained Equations with Random Forest (MICE-Ranger) algorithm (Section 3.1), which has proven to be one of the most efficient algorithms to impute missing hydrometeorological data (Jing et al., 2022).

Fig. 3 shows the time series associated with the internal variables of the four beehives after the imputation procedure was completed. To improve the legibility of the graph, the primary axis features are the four internal temperature variables and weight, while relative humidity is represented on the secondary axis. These graphs reveal a great data variability, particularly in humidity. Additionally abrupt changes in weight, attributed to different hive activities such as feeding or harvesting, also underscore the challenging nature of the datasets. Nevertheless, it is noticeable that, overall, the beehive variables exhibit a similar behavior in the same seasons of the year.

The fact of having four separate readings of a singular response variable in different locations of the hive (temperature) suggests the potential issue of forecasting variables that are closely correlated. To assess this hypothesis, a Pearson correlation test was conducted for each pair of response variables. Fig. 4 illustrates the correlation among the different internal variables of the analyzed beehives. A color code has been used to identify variables that exhibit a high correlation with each other. Intense plum color represents a high positive correlation, while intense blue indicates a high negative correlation. For enhanced graphical interpretation, circle diameters are scaled based on the absolute value of the Pearson correlation coefficient. Larger circles visually represent high correlations between variables, while smaller circles denote lower correlations. Within the matrix's lower triangular section, correlation coefficients for each value pair are illustrated, with asterisk notations above the diagonal indicating the significance codes of the associated p-values from Pearson correlation test, with '*', '**', and '***' indicating that the p-values obtained are statistically significant at confidence levels 0.05, 0.01, and 0.001, respectively. Results were considered statistically significant when p-values were less than 0.05.

The analysis of Fig. 4 highlights a notable lack of significant linear correlation between weight and the remaining internal variables (temperatures and humidity), regardless of the hive being examined. However, a clear positive correlation is present among the different temperatures (measured at distinct hive points), along with an inversely proportional correlation between temperatures and humidity, i.e., that lower temperatures correspond to higher hive humidity. Considering

Fig. 3. Time series of internal temperatures (different types of lines in blue, pink, purple, and black colors), internal relative humidity (blue dotted line), and weight (orange line) of the four hives analyzed: Hagen, Ingolstadt, Vohburg, and Waltrop. Temperature and weight are located on the main axis (left), and relative humidity on the secondary axis (right).

all the hives, 53.3% of the Pearson correlation coefficients between the internal variables were found to be significant. This distribution is not equal in all hives, with the Ingolstadt, Hagen and Vohburg hives having the highest number of significant Pearson correlation coefficients (all of them with a proportion equal to 66.7%) and, in contrast, the Waltrop

hive, which contains only 13.3% of significant correlations, has the lowest number of significant Pearson correlation coefficients.

In light of these results, it becomes essential to acknowledge the existence of highly correlated variables in this experimental design, and the need to properly address them. This together with the proven

Fig. 4. Pearson's correlation coefficients between the different endogenous variables in the Hagen (top-left), Ingolstadt (top-right), Vohburg (bottom-left), and Waltrop (bottom-right) hives. The plum color represents a direct correlation and the blue color an inverse correlation. Both color intensity and circle size are directly proportional to the magnitude of the correlation. Correlation coefficients are presented below the main diagonal, with the significance level of these coefficients indicated above the diagonal. Asterisks '*', '**', and '***' indicate that the p-values obtained are statistically significant at confidence levels 0.05, 0.01, and 0.001, respectively.

data imperfections make these datasets challenging to be used in any predictive model.

3. Statistical methods

This section is devoted to present the methodology applied to the data sets collected. First, the method applied to the missing data for imputation is described. Next, the multivariate models used to fit and predict internal variables with the final data sets are described. In addition, the cross-validation framework considered to measure generalization performance is detailed. Finally, the software and hardware details for the implementation are presented.

3.1. Imputation algorithm

The MICE-Ranger algorithm iteratively imputes each missing data by using a series of prediction algorithms (random forest in this case) that use the remaining variables as predictors. The algorithm works as follows:

1. Replaces missing values in each variable with temporary 'placeholder' values derived solely from the non-missing values existing for that variable.
2. Each variable undergoes analysis through a random forest algorithm, which employs the remaining variables to predict missing data for the reference variable. The resulting predictions are used to update the values for the missing data of this variable.

3. This process continues until all specified values have been imputed.

Iterations are run until convergence is reached. Typically, no more than five iterations are required.

3.2. Statistical models

Let T be the time that n variables are observed and let y_t and c_t , $t \in \{1, \dots, T\}$, be the vectors corresponding to the response and covariate variables at time t , respectively. In the univariate case, the notation does not use bold type, i.e., as y_t and c_t .

3.2.1. Dynamic factor analysis model

Dynamic factor analysis (DFA) models try to explain the time variation in a set of n observed time series using linear combinations of a set of m hidden random walks, where $m < n$ (Holmes et al., 2023a). A DFA model is a particular case of Multivariate Auto-Regressive State-Space (MARSS) model with the following structure:

$$x_t = x_{t-1} + v_t \quad v_t \sim MVN(0, Q),$$

$$y_t = Zx_t + \tau + Cc_t + e_t \quad e_t \sim MVN(0, R), \tag{1}$$

$$x_0 \sim MVN(\pi, \Lambda),$$

where matrix C represents the effects of the covariates on the observations, Z is the matrix of factor loadings, and τ acts as a offset to

the equation. Note that there are two errors, v_t is the process error at time t having multivariate normal (MVN) distribution with mean $\mathbf{0}$ and covariance matrix \mathbf{Q} , and e_t is the observation error at time t having MVN distribution with mean $\mathbf{0}$ and covariance matrix \mathbf{R} . In addition, the initial random vector \mathbf{x}_0 has a MVN distribution with mean $\boldsymbol{\pi}$ and covariance matrix $\boldsymbol{\Lambda}$.

3.2.2. Combining data from multiple time series

This method considers the case where multiple time series exist and all they are used to estimate a common underlying state process or common underlying parameters. A model combining data from multiple time series (CMTS) allows to analyze data from populations containing time series from different study methods (Holmes et al., 2023a). The model is expressed as follows:

$$\mathbf{x}_t = \mathbf{B}\mathbf{x}_{t-1} + \mathbf{v} + \mathbf{v}_t \quad \mathbf{v}_t \sim MVN(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{Q}), \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{y}_t = \mathbf{Z}\mathbf{x}_t + \boldsymbol{\tau} + \mathbf{C}\mathbf{c}_t + \mathbf{e}_t \quad \mathbf{e}_t \sim MVN(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{R}),$$

where the matrix \mathbf{B} allows interaction between processes, \mathbf{v} is a vector describing the mean trend, and the correlation of the process deviations is determined by the structure of the matrix \mathbf{Q} . \mathbf{Z} is a design matrix of 0s and 1s, $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ is a vector of bias adjustments, and the correlation structure of observation matrices is specified with the matrix \mathbf{R} .

3.2.3. A general multivariate auto-regressive state-space model

A general multivariate auto-regressive state-space (MARSG) model can be defined by assuming that the dynamic factor analysis has trend and seasonal cycle (Holmes et al., 2023a,b),

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x}_t &= \mathbf{B}\mathbf{x}_{t-1} + \mathbf{v}_t, & \mathbf{v}_t &\sim MVN(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{Q}), \\ \mathbf{y}_t &= \mathbf{Z}\mathbf{x}_t + \mathbf{C}\mathbf{c}_t + \mathbf{e}_t, & \mathbf{e}_t &\sim MVN(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{R}), \\ \mathbf{x}_0 &\sim MVN(\boldsymbol{\pi}, \boldsymbol{\Lambda}), \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{Z} is a design matrix of 0s and 1s, such that the dynamic factors are defined. \mathbf{B} is a design matrix of 0s, 1s and -1 s, such that both trend and seasonal dynamic components are introduced; the factors for temperature and relative humidity have both trend and seasonal components, with a frequency in the cycle equal to 5 referring to the 5 observations per day; and the factor for the weight has only dynamic trend component.

3.2.4. Vector autoregressive model

A Vector Autoregressive model of order p , VAR(p), is a generalization of the univariate autoregressive model for predicting time series. It is one of the most efficient and flexible models for multivariate time series analysis. The VAR(p) model with exogenous variables is defined as follows:

$$\mathbf{y}_t = \boldsymbol{\mu} + \sum_{i=1}^p \mathbf{A}_i \mathbf{y}_{t-i} + \mathbf{C}\mathbf{c}_t + \mathbf{e}_t, \quad t = p+1, \dots, T, \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{A}_1, \dots, \mathbf{A}_p$ are fixed coefficient matrices, $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ is the vector of intercept terms, \mathbf{C} is the coefficient matrix of exogenous variables, and \mathbf{e}_t is the vector of error terms, being a white noise process.

The number of lags can be determined using different information criteria such as Akaike Information (AIC), Hannan-Quinn (HQ), Schwarz (SC), or Akaike's Final Prediction Error (FPE) (Zhang et al., 2023).

3.2.5. Vector error correction model

The Vector Error Correction (VEC) model serves as an extension of the Vector Autoregressive (VAR) framework, specifically addressing the long-term equilibrium association among the variables. This relationship, termed cointegration, denotes that the variables share an underlying stochastic trend and maintain long-run integration.

The VEC(p) model with exogenous variables is defined as:

$$\Delta \mathbf{y}_t = \boldsymbol{\mu} + \sum_{i=1}^p \boldsymbol{\Pi}_i \Delta \mathbf{y}_{t-i} + \boldsymbol{\Gamma} \mathbf{y}_{t-1} + \mathbf{C}\mathbf{c}_t + \mathbf{e}_t, \quad t = p+1, \dots, T, \quad (5)$$

where $\Delta \mathbf{y}_t$ is the vector of first differences of \mathbf{y}_t , $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ is the vector of constant terms, $\boldsymbol{\Pi}_i$ are de coefficient matrices associated with the i th lags, $\boldsymbol{\Gamma}$ is a matrix capturing the long-term cointegration relationship between the response variables, \mathbf{C} is the coefficient matrix of exogenous variables, and \mathbf{e}_t is the vector of errors (assumed to follow a multivariate white noise process).

3.3. Error metrics

The assessment metric employed to summarize the error introduced by the models is the mean absolute error (MAE), which calculates the average absolute value of the straight-line distance between actual values and those predicted by the model. This error is measured on the same scale as the data, facilitating its interpretation. It is expressed as:

$$MAE = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N |y_i - \hat{y}_i|}{N} \quad (6)$$

where \hat{y}_i denotes the prediction provided by the model, y_i represents their real values, and N is the number of predicted values.

3.4. Cross-validation

For model performance assessment, a cross-validation framework is implemented focusing on the temporal dimension. This involves the creation of training and testing sets that account for the chronological order of the data. Employing a rolling window approach (Zivot and Wang, 2006), a widely used technique for back-testing statistical models on historical data, the evaluation of both stability and predictive accuracy is performed.

The time series is initially divided into a training sample and a test sample, both conforming to predetermined sizes. The fitting phase is conducted on the training sample, resulting in the generation of γ -step ahead predictions and the MAE is calculated by comparing the predictions with the test sample. Afterward, the training sample is shifted δ steps forward, leading to the creation of a new training and test set, and the procedures of fitting, prediction, and error calculation are then repeated for the new dataset. This process is recurrently performed for a set number of k iterations (k -fold rolling window cross-validation) or until no more γ -step predictions are possible.

Once this process is finished, the mean absolute errors obtained in each iteration for each variable are summarized using the mean and standard deviation, aiding in the interpretation of results.

3.5. Implementation

The R programming language was employed to write the code for conducting tasks related to data imputation, model fitting, prediction, and cross-validation for the previously specified models (R Core Team, 2020). For executing the missing data imputation process was *miceRanger* package (Wilson, 2020) was used. In order to carry out the fitting and prediction process in the different models analyzed, the implemented code is based on the packages *MARSS* (Holmes et al., 2023a) for DFA, CMTS, and MARSG models, *vars* (Pfaff, 2008) for the VAR model, and *tsDyn* (Fabio Di Narzo et al., 2009) for VEC model. The R source code is provided upon request to the authors.

The experiments were carried out on a compute node with a processor Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-10700 CPU @ 2.90 GHz and 32 GB RAM.

4. Experimental settings and results

This section presents the experimental settings and results for fitting and prediction.

Fig. 5. MAEs means obtained after 1-day forecasts for the six response variables considering the different hive analyses: Hagen (top left), Ingolstadt (top right), Vohburg (bottom left) and Waltrop (bottom right). Three lines are marked on each radar plot, the first one represents the zero value, the third one is the maximum MAE means obtained in each hive and the central line is the midpoint between both.

4.1. Experimental settings

The specifications of the experiments conducted to obtain the results presented in this article are based on the datasets presented in Section 2, which contain sensor data from 6 internal variables (response or endogenous variables) and 8 variables providing information about the meteorological conditions to which they are exposed (covariate or exogenous variables).

Understanding external interventions that beehives may have undergone, such as the feeding or harvesting processes, is a valuable piece of information. Consequently, a new variable was formulated to capture extreme weight fluctuations. This involved the computation of differences between successive weight measurements. Subsequently, the 2.5 and 97.5 percentiles were calculated, designating values outside this range as extreme weight variations, attributed to external influences, such as the addition or removal of hive frames, health status assessments, introduction of artificial feeding, or product harvesting, among other factors. This variable proved instrumental in rectifying instances of extreme weight fluctuations. Thus, the models were formulated using 6 response variables. Regarding the number of covariates, the VAR and VEC models utilized the previously described 9 variables the 8 variables collected by sensors pertain to external meteorological conditions, along with the variable capturing extreme weight changes induced by external actions, whereas the DFA, CMTS, and MARS models employed a total of 13 covariates. This augmentation involved the inclusion of four supplementary dummy variables to incorporate information pertaining to the time at which the measurements were taken.

For all analyzed hives, a training series of one year and four months was considered, comprising a total of 2425 values for each variable after preprocessing. A 100-fold cross-validation was undertaken, with increments of $\delta = 5$ observations in order to make 5- and 15- steps ahead predictions which correspond to 1- and 3-day, respectively. In order

to maintain the optimal functionality of the models, standardization of variables was implemented.

The following provides information on the specific configurations of each of the studied models:

- In DFA model, the optimal outcomes were observed in the configuration where the model incorporated a total of $m = 5$ different random walks. This model designates matrix Q as an identity matrix, and matrix R is specified as a diagonal matrix with identical values along its diagonal. Matrix Z is constructed as an unconstrained matrix, with the upper triangle (excluding the diagonal) set to zero.
- In the CMTS model, matrices Q and R are diagonal and unequal, i.e., off-diagonal values are set to zero and on-diagonal values can be different from each other. Matrix Z is an identity matrix and B is a vector allowing distinct values.
- In the MARS model, matrix R is diagonal and equal; matrix Q is diagonal and unequal, for the trend and seasonal components, with a frequency in the cycle equal to 5 (number of observations per day). Finally, with the design matrix Z three dynamic factors have been defined: a factor used for the four interior temperatures, one for the relative humidity, and another one for the weight.
- In the VAR model, both the constant and trend of each time series are accounted for, and the selection of the optimal number of lags in the model was based on the AIC criterion, which demonstrated superior performance. The predetermined limit for delays is 20.
- In the VEC model, both the constant and trend of each time series are taken into account. Furthermore, the Johansen cointegration test was utilized to ascertain the number of statistically significant cointegration relationships (Gianfreda et al., 2023). Finally, the MAE served as the criterion for selecting the optimal number of lags, providing the most accurate results. The predetermined limit of delays is 20.

Table 2

Mean ± standard deviation of MAE derived from different models in the fitting process of the internal variables of the Hagen, Ingolstadt, Vohburg, and Waltrop hives over a period of sixteen months.

		MARSS models						Vector time series models				
		DFA		CMTS		MARSG		VAR		VEC		
Hagen	R. Hum.	3.785	± 0.250	4.842	± 0.078	4.122	± 0.336	2.494	± 0.151	2.983	± 0.231	
	Temp. 1	1.115	± 0.073	1.743	± 0.083	1.444	± 0.023	0.599	± 0.027	0.642	± 0.040	
	Temp. 2	1.357	± 0.096	1.379	± 0.087	2.293	± 0.055	0.751	± 0.022	0.990	± 0.051	
	Temp. 3	1.187	± 0.105	1.661	± 0.090	1.385	± 0.021	0.629	± 0.038	0.679	± 0.053	
	Temp. 4	1.537	± 0.165	1.532	± 0.136	1.702	± 0.061	0.749	± 0.054	0.987	± 0.072	
	Weight	0.376	± 0.022	0.213	± 0.013	0.355	± 0.013	0.106	± 0.006	0.111	± 0.006	
Ingolstadt	R. Hum.	2.170	± 0.053	2.714	± 0.152	2.321	± 0.056	1.646	± 0.056	1.739	± 0.058	
	Temp. 1	0.682	± 0.022	1.036	± 0.053	1.583	± 0.027	0.464	± 0.025	0.472	± 0.024	
	Temp. 2	0.976	± 0.020	1.070	± 0.057	1.380	± 0.026	0.539	± 0.032	0.553	± 0.033	
	Temp. 3	0.909	± 0.041	0.862	± 0.056	1.613	± 0.174	0.647	± 0.061	0.651	± 0.060	
	Temp. 4	0.942	± 0.044	0.925	± 0.066	2.528	± 0.156	0.667	± 0.062	0.675	± 0.063	
	Weight	0.154	± 0.008	0.161	± 0.012	0.250	± 0.006	0.066	± 0.001	0.068	± 0.001	
Vohburg	R. Hum.	3.634	± 0.122	4.135	± 0.110	3.603	± 0.107	2.473	± 0.087	1.960	± 0.198	
	Temp. 1	1.010	± 0.035	1.617	± 0.054	1.635	± 0.029	0.679	± 0.028	0.541	± 0.067	
	Temp. 2	1.437	± 0.033	1.777	± 0.041	2.079	± 0.029	1.002	± 0.042	0.702	± 0.119	
	Temp. 3	0.888	± 0.012	0.798	± 0.016	1.915	± 0.036	0.500	± 0.022	0.376	± 0.027	
	Temp. 4	0.939	± 0.015	0.915	± 0.020	2.133	± 0.036	0.661	± 0.012	0.479	± 0.019	
	Weight	0.163	± 0.003	0.174	± 0.009	0.241	± 0.004	0.091	± 0.002	0.088	± 0.002	
Waltrop	R. Hum.	6.928	± 0.195	6.512	± 0.132	7.887	± 0.234	5.363	± 0.219	5.724	± 0.398	
	Temp. 1	1.544	± 0.041	1.124	± 0.028	3.485	± 0.135	0.661	± 0.011	0.732	± 0.015	
	Temp. 2	1.702	± 0.069	1.617	± 0.067	5.527	± 0.224	1.399	± 0.058	1.456	± 0.063	
	Temp. 3	1.038	± 0.014	0.948	± 0.009	4.154	± 0.102	0.865	± 0.002	0.857	± 0.011	
	Temp. 4	1.487	± 0.010	1.035	± 0.011	3.830	± 0.175	0.775	± 0.010	0.847	± 0.036	
	Weight	0.246	± 0.004	0.143	± 0.004	0.463	± 0.009	0.061	± 0.002	0.062	± 0.002	

4.2. Experimental results

This subsection will present the results regarding model fitting and forecasting of internal variables for each studied hive. Firstly, Table 2 presents the means and standard deviations of the MAEs acquired through the model fitting process. In general terms, the VAR model yielded the optimal fitting, contrasting with the MARSG model, which demonstrated the least favorable fitting. When differentiating between time series models (VAR and VEC) and linear regression models (DFA, CMTS, and MARSG), a clear divergence becomes apparent with time series models clearly providing a more effective fitting.

Fig. 5 shows, through a radar plot, the mean of the MAEs obtained by the five models following 1-day ahead predictions for the six endogenous variables. Both the fitting results (Table 2) and the 1-day prediction outcomes (Fig. 5) highlight a clear difference in the performance of linear regression and time series models. VAR and VEC models outperform linear regression models in the prediction of variables for 1-day ahead prediction in this multivariate and highly correlated internal variables hive context. The same conclusion is achieved for the 3-days ahead predictions. From now on, we will focus on analyzing VAR and VEC results.

Concerning lag selection, Table 3 displays the most frequently selected hyperparameters by VAR and VEC models, respectively, across 100 iterations of cross-validation. This configuration was employed to measure the complexity of each model, i.e., the number of parameters to be tuned in each, alongside the runtime (in seconds) required for the fitting process.

In Table 3, it is illustrated how VEC models tend to choose a lower number of lags than the VAR model, regardless of the analyzed dataset. This leads to a noticeable reduction in model complexity as well as the time required for its fitting. The reduction in both fitting time and complexity renders the VEC model more compelling for handling this kind of highly correlated data.

Table 4 presents the predictive accuracies yielded by VAR and VEC models for the six internal variables after the cross-validation process, particularly focusing on 1- and 3-day ahead predictions. The table includes the mean and standard deviation of the MAE for both models, with the one achieving the lower prediction error highlighted in bold. It can be observed that the VEC model provides more accurate predictions

Table 3

Hyperparameters mostly selected through cross-validation for VAR and VEC models in the Hagen, Ingolstadt, Vohburg, and Waltrop hives. p(%) represents the count of lags and the overall percentage of times this value has been selected, while r(%) represents the number of cointegration relationships mostly selected, and the total proportion of time this specific value has been selected. Model complexity and fitting time (in seconds) were assessed across models employing the most commonly selected hyperparameters.

Hive	Model	Hyperparameters	Complexity	Fitting time
Hagen	VAR	p = 16 (100%)	642	0.170
	VEC	p = 2 (100%) r = 5 (100%)	156	0.020
Ingolstadt	VAR	p = 16 (100%)	642	0.190
	VEC	p = 6 (64%) r = 3 (96%)	288	0.040
Vohburg	VAR	p = 16 (51%)	642	0.200
	VEC	p = 2 (53%) r = 4 (100%)	150	0.020
Waltrop	VAR	p = 19 (100%)	750	0.210
	VEC	p = 3 (58%) r = 4 (100%)	186	0.030

than the VAR model in 91.67% of cases for the Hagen beehive, 75% for the Ingolstadt and Vohburg beehives, and 66.67% for the Waltrop beehive.

The obtained results suggest that the VAR and VEC models are more competitive than the considered regression models in this context. When compared, the VEC model has certain advantages over the VAR model, with slightly better predictive results. In particular, it has lower model complexity and lower computational cost, which translates into more competitive fitting times. These characteristics make it more suitable for inclusion in a decision support system in a big data environment with highly correlated data. In addition, it stands out as the model that best fits the experimental design by incorporating cointegration relationships in its formulation.

5. Discussion

Precision apiculture has undergone a relevant development in recent years. Currently, new projects and research efforts continue to emerge, focusing on the creation of integrated architectures for monitoring bee colonies such as those in Cota et al. (2023) or Hamza et al. (2023). Some of these projects employ data processing exclusively to

Table 4

Comparison between the MAE's mean \pm standard deviation obtained after 1- and 3-days ahead forecast of VAR and VEC models for the six response variables considering the different hive analyses: Hagen (top left), Ingolstadt (top right), Vohburg (bottom left) and Waltrop (bottom right). In bold is marked the best result obtained.

		VAR		VEC				VAR		VEC			
Hagen	RH	1	2.499	\pm 1.414	2.392	\pm 1.440	Ingolstadt	RH	1	2.778	\pm 1.846	2.866	\pm 1.669
		3	2.809	\pm 1.159	2.739	\pm 1.163			3	3.638	\pm 2.280	3.845	\pm 2.245
	T1	1	0.578	\pm 0.397	0.552	\pm 0.404		T1	1	0.675	\pm 0.793	0.646	\pm 0.797
		3	0.646	\pm 0.332	0.614	\pm 0.353			3	0.747	\pm 0.717	0.739	\pm 0.717
	T2	1	1.207	\pm 1.079	1.181	\pm 1.163		T2	1	0.785	\pm 0.988	0.731	\pm 0.986
		3	1.847	\pm 1.407	1.859	\pm 1.504			3	0.924	\pm 0.898	0.910	\pm 0.887
	T3	1	0.589	\pm 0.386	0.571	\pm 0.385		T3	1	1.178	\pm 1.835	1.122	\pm 1.894
		3	0.678	\pm 0.339	0.663	\pm 0.377			3	1.747	\pm 1.939	1.685	\pm 1.950
	T4	1	1.029	\pm 0.714	1.025	\pm 0.651		T4	1	1.012	\pm 1.560	1.003	\pm 1.582
		3	1.456	\pm 0.927	1.442	\pm 0.839			3	1.205	\pm 1.274	1.245	\pm 1.312
	W	1	0.140	\pm 0.165	0.135	\pm 0.179		W	1	0.104	\pm 0.071	0.103	\pm 0.067
		3	0.275	\pm 0.261	0.273	\pm 0.327			3	0.157	\pm 0.099	0.152	\pm 0.091
Vohburg	RH	1	3.718	\pm 2.493	3.366	\pm 3.080	Waltrop	RH	1	9.980	\pm 10.326	10.802	\pm 10.127
		3	4.503	\pm 2.312	3.802	\pm 2.506			3	11.929	\pm 10.617	13.936	\pm 9.927
	T1	1	0.707	\pm 0.426	0.692	\pm 0.440		T1	1	0.777	\pm 0.489	0.758	\pm 0.478
		3	0.837	\pm 0.538	0.783	\pm 0.341			3	1.035	\pm 0.501	1.006	\pm 0.452
	T2	1	1.215	\pm 1.460	1.189	\pm 1.787		T2	1	2.502	\pm 2.810	2.358	\pm 2.934
		3	1.570	\pm 1.972	1.504	\pm 2.233			3	4.151	\pm 4.221	3.897	\pm 4.348
	T3	1	0.783	\pm 0.581	0.839	\pm 0.768		T3	1	1.248	\pm 1.061	1.104	\pm 0.956
		3	1.299	\pm 0.918	1.266	\pm 0.819			3	2.002	\pm 1.496	1.815	\pm 1.487
	T4	1	1.131	\pm 0.846	0.934	\pm 0.849		T4	1	1.448	\pm 1.266	1.566	\pm 1.332
		3	1.723	\pm 1.235	1.430	\pm 1.162			3	2.221	\pm 1.433	2.369	\pm 1.471
	W	1	0.166	\pm 0.139	0.177	\pm 0.138		W	1	0.067	\pm 0.047	0.063	\pm 0.043
		3	0.290	\pm 0.236	0.312	\pm 0.243			3	0.121	\pm 0.071	0.112	\pm 0.075

analyze and present beekeepers with parameters regarding the current state of their beehives (Torky et al., 2023). Despite substantial progress in monitoring systems, there is a scarcity of open databases that facilitate the research community's advancement in developing statistical models for the analysis, classification, and prediction in the context of sensor data collected from bee colonies. Besides, the statistical analysis of data obtained through sensors becomes a challenging task due to the imperfect nature of the databases. In this work, the used databases exhibit a significant percentage of missing and erroneous data, varying from 1.8% to 6.7%. The problem of inaccurate sensor data in the field of precision beekeeping is common. Evidence of this lies in the fact that some authors are actively seeking models to mitigate prediction errors stemming from the variability induced by sensor imprecision in predictor variables. An example of such efforts is the work of Jia et al. (2023) who proposed an algorithm that combines a linear regression model and a Kalman filter to mitigate the impact of temperature variations on the weight of bee colonies caused by fluctuations in ambient temperature. Another instance can be found in Degenfellner and Templ (2024), where robust algorithms were applied for signal extraction and regression to address the influence of outliers on hive weight dynamics modeling and to facilitate the identification of substantial changes in dynamics in order to alert beekeepers for potential events that could harm hive health.

The limited availability of open databases and the challenge associated with conducting statistical analyses on such data constitute two factors justifying the limited number of research articles focused on making predictions regarding internal variables of beehives. To the best of the authors' knowledge, only five articles have been published for the issue of making predictions about any of the internal variables considered in this study (temperature, weight or humidity). Even more, there is a lack of research in the application and development of multivariate models to predict internal conditions in beehives. In this study, it has been observed that time series models fit data of sensorized internal conditions of beehives better than state-space autoregressive models. The same behavior is also reflected in predictions, with larger

errors observed when using state-space autoregressive models instead of employing vector autoregressive time series models. Furthermore, among the studied vector autoregressive time series models, the VEC-based approach emerges as the one striking the best balance between complexity, computational time, fitting, and prediction quality.

Focusing on the VEC-based approach, the MAEs in the 1-day ahead temperatures forecasts range from 0.6 to 2.4 °C, depending on the sensor's location and the hive analyzed. Remarkably, the sensor associated with temperature (T1) displays superior prediction stability, regardless of the hive being analyzed. Positioned at location E (Fig. 1), the farthest from the entrance hole (A), is less affected by external temperature fluctuations. On the other hand, the MAEs in the 1-day ahead humidity range from 2.4 to 10.9%, where the highest error was observed in the Waltrop hive, significantly deviating from the errors obtained for the remaining hives. This can be attributed to the substantial variability present in the relative humidity data towards the latter part of the time series for this variable, displaying a markedly distinct behavior compared to the rest of the series. Finally, the MAEs for 1-day ahead weight predictions range from 63 to 178g. In general, considering the variability in values exhibited by these variables across various hives, it is reasonable to state that the obtained errors are entirely manageable.

In order to conduct a comparison of advances on this topic, it is necessary to consider the significant heterogeneity that exists among the different articles, revealing notable differences in crucial characteristics such as the variables used for predictions, the models employed, the chosen prediction horizon, the error metrics applied, the used databases, and, of course, the univariate or multivariate nature of the approach. The considerable heterogeneity poses a significant challenge in making a direct comparison between outcomes. To enhance the reader's overall understanding of similarities and differences among articles predicting hive internal temperature, weight, and/or humidity, a summary has been presented in Table 5, which incorporates the most relevant characteristics of the prediction models presented in these articles and the Vector Error Correction (VEC) model utilized in the current study. Enabling the elaboration of a more detailed discussion on the comparison of the various proposals.

Table 5
Overview of the main attributes of scientific articles relevant to this study (temperature, weight, and humidity of beehives).

	Braga et al. (2021)	Robustillo et al. (2022)	Anwar et al. (2022)	Rigakis et al. (2023)	Anwar et al. (2023)	This work
Hives	5	3	3	1	11	4
Model	Combination of neural networks	Vector auto-regressive model	Random forest	Additive regression model	Self-attention encoders	Vector error correction model
Multivariate prediction	No	Yes	No	No	No	Yes
Response variables	Temperature	Temperature, humidity, and weight	Weight	Humidity	Weight	Temperatures (4), humidity, and weight
Total	1	3	1	1	1	6
Covariates	Internal: humidity, mean fanning, weight, and average hive noise. External: temperature	External: Temperature, humidity, rainfall, brightness, windspeed, particulate matter (2), air pressure, and weight changes due external actions	Internal: Temperature, humidity, atmospheric pressure, CO ₂ levels, acoustic variables, vibrations, and weight. External: meteorological variables	Internal: Temperature, weight, CO ₂ levels, bee entrances and exits, hive vibration (5) and total concentration of volatile organic compounds	Internal: Temperature, humidity, atmospheric pressure, CO ₂ levels, acoustic variables, vibrations, and weight. External: meteorological variables	External: Temperature, humidity, rainfall, brightness, windspeed, particulate matter (2), air pressure, and weight changes due external actions
Total	5	9	34	11	36	9
Forecasting	Per hive	Per hive	Global	Per hive	Per sensor system	Per hive
Cross-validation	No	100-fold rolling window	5-fold	No	8-system	100-fold rolling window
Prediction horizon	2-h, 4-h, 1-day	1-day, 3-days, 7-days	1-day	1-day	1-day	1-day, 3-days
Error metric	RMSE	MAE	MAE	MAPE	RMSE/frame	MAE
Time cost	No	Yes	No	No	No	Yes
Addressing correlation	No	No	No	No	No	Yes

As can be observed, most of these articles (Braga et al., 2021; Anwar et al., 2022; Rigakis et al., 2023; Anwar et al., 2023) use univariate predictive models, indicating their focus on predicting a single variable of interest. Furthermore, it is important to highlight that all these models use internal beehive variables as covariates (regressor variables in the model). Consequently, these proposed models would experience a loss of reliability when used in a real prediction scenario, as they depend on future values of hive conditions that are unknown, and no model is suggested for predicting them. The inclusion of multivariate prediction algorithms, those capable of jointly addressing the prediction of multiple internal hive variables, is a distinctive feature found in the work of Robustillo et al. (2022). That approach and ours employ the inherent beehive variables as response variables, resulting in a multivariate model. The covariates utilized encompass external meteorological conditions and external actions that induce changes in hive weight, whose future values can be known. This renders the models proposed by both studies applicable to a real predictive environment.

Regarding the number of hives investigated, Anwar et al. (2023) analyze a total of 11 hives, as their primary objective was to compare different sensor systems. However, the hives were placed in only 3 different locations. The rest of the articles are conducted using a specific sensor system, resulting in a more reduced number of analyzed hives. Another characteristic closely related to the number of hives studied is the use of these hives to make predictions. For example, Anwar et al. (2022) uses data from all hives to train and make predictions, creating a common data set for the three hives analyzed. In contrast, Anwar et al. (2023) make predictions distinguishing by the sensor system used. The rest of the articles make predictions for each hive independently. The practice of presenting results individually for each hive introduces an additional challenge in terms of how to incorporate this information. The graphs and tables needed to do so become less interpretable as the number of hives (and, of course, the number of variables to predict)

increases. Consequently, articles presenting results for each hive do not analyze more than 5 different hives. Here, 4 different hives are examined, a number slightly larger than the average number of hives analyzed in approaches making predictions based on the specific hive being examined. In addition, it should be noted that the number of variables to be predicted is 6, larger than the variables predicted by others, which translates into a substantially larger volume of results to show and compare.

Another characteristic that exhibits significant divergence among different approaches is the inclusion or absence of a cross-validation process. Cross-validation provides information on the stability of statistical models in their predictive task and ensures that the obtained results are independent of the selected training and test sets. Braga et al. (2021) and Rigakis et al. (2023) did not use cross-validation processes, and therefore, the generalization performance has not been analyzed. The other approaches considered different types of cross-validation processes. Similar to this study, Robustillo et al. (2022) opted for a cross-validation process that considers the temporality of the data, making it the most appropriate for use with models predicting time series data. Anwar et al. (2022) chose the typical 5-fold cross-validation, whereas Anwar et al. (2023) used an 8-system cross-validation since their objective was to analyze the behavior of different sensor systems. In general, considering that sensor data has a strong temporal component, the rolling-window cross-validation model used here is more consistent for evaluating the stability of models applied to historical data, as it takes this temporality into account when creating the validation and test sets.

An aspect that all these approaches is conducting predictions with a 1-day ahead forecast horizon. Despite this common ground, there is a mismatch in the selection of error metrics for measurement. The wide range of chosen error metrics introduces variability, making it challenging to conduct clear result comparisons. The most prominent

example is found in the article by Anwar et al. (2023), where the chosen error metric is the square root of the mean squared error (RMSE) for each frame within the beehive. This choice is influenced by the fact that not all analyzed beehives have the same number of frames. The challenge arises from the absence of information regarding the frame count in the results, making them entirely incomparable. Another noteworthy case arises in the article by Rigakis et al. (2023) which reported certain metric values, such as negative R^2 , which are theoretically impossible, since R^2 ranges in $[0,1]$. Regarding the outcomes obtained by Braga et al. (2021), they achieve good results in predictions at 2- and 4-h. However, they acknowledge that the model fails to reproduce temperature patterns when making predictions for a 1-day ahead horizon. Anwar et al. (2022) utilized the information provided by all beehives to create a common dataset for training and making prediction. In that context, they achieved a general MAE of 200g for 1-day weight predictions (they did not make a distinction among beehives when making predictions), whereas the proposed VEC approach provides MAEs between 63 and 178g for the analyzed hives. Lastly, the same error order is kept when comparing the 1-day results of the VEC-based approach with the model proposed by Robustillo et al. (2022) for the three common variables -relative humidity, temperature (T1), and weight-. In particular, when the hive has a high correlation, the proposed approach outperforms the ones in Robustillo et al. (2022), while in cases of low correlation, this improvement is not observed. This indicates that the VEC-based approach is more suitable for addressing the challenge of predicting highly correlated internal variables.

There is a great variability in the models used to address the task of predicting internal variables in beehives. Among the selected models are neural networks, additive regression models, random forests for regression, and proprietary vector time series models. These models consist of a highly variable number of parameters, leading to different levels of difficulty when fitting the model to a dataset, this results in diverse fitting times. While the time a model takes to adjust to a dataset is crucial for considering it suitable for real-time prediction tasks, most authors do not conduct computational cost analyses. Computational times are only addressed by Robustillo et al. (2022) and the present study. When comparing fitting times, the VEC-based approach is much faster in the adjustment phase than the model proposed by Robustillo et al. (2022). The fitting times for the latter ranged between 14 and 25 min, depending on the analyzed beehive, to adjust a model with three predictor variables. In contrast, the VEC-based approach achieves a fitting time of less than a second to adjust the model for predicting twice as many variables. This makes the VEC-based approach much more suitable for real-time model fitting.

To the best of the authors' knowledge, the challenge of predicting highly correlated variables in sensor-equipped beehives had not been addressed previously. Certain variables are sensor-placement-dependent, such as temperature. Sensors situated near the brood are less influenced by external conditions, whereas those placed towards the periphery will be more affected (Alleri et al., 2023). Therefore, it is important to predict the hive temperature at different points in the hive, which requires solving a multivariate prediction problem with highly correlated variables. This study stands out for being the only one that takes into account the existence of highly correlated response variables when predicting internal hive conditions. The VEC-based approach properly fit the right experimental statistical design by incorporating cointegration equations to address the challenge of highly correlated response variables. Therefore, this work is a natural continuation of the previously published study (Robustillo et al., 2022), which, despite predicting multiple internal hive variables, did not address the issue of predicting highly correlated variables.

The present study is subject to certain limitations. All colonies under investigation were situated in Germany, and despite the examination of beehives from two geographically separated regions, caution must be exercised when trying to extend the results to other locations with

different climatology and to precision beekeeping systems collecting other types of variables. Nevertheless, the analyzed models are capable of incorporating diverse variables obtained through sensors and can be adjusted to other architectural frameworks. Besides, the results could be significantly improved by using data collections based on high quality sensors and communication systems. In addition, databases of high quality (characterized by a low incidence of imputed data) have been selected to minimize the influence of the chosen imputation algorithm on the predictive accuracy of the model. Greater proportions of imputed data could lead the algorithm to train on less dependable values, deviating from actual data and potentially compromising the predictive accuracy.

6. Conclusion

In recent years, there has been a relevant advance in the scientific literature on precision beekeeping. However, this progress remains remarkably limited when addressing predictive models concerning hive internal variables, such as weight, temperature, and humidity. There is a research gap on predictive models addressing highly correlated response variables for precision beekeeping, which are aligned with proper experimental designs and presenting a low computational cost.

This study contributes to fill this research gap. The VEC-based approach stands out as the most suitable one for experimental design, maintaining a commendable equilibrium among fitting, prediction accuracy, and computational efficiency. The incorporation of cointegration variables has proven instrumental in addressing the challenge of predicting highly correlated variables, thereby ensuring that the VEC-based approach yields reliable predictions regarding the internal conditions of the hive. This approach is suitable for integration into a decision support system within a real-time big data analysis environment. The use of such models can anticipate the needs and challenges faced by bees, ensuring their well-being and enhancing the profitability of beekeepers.

In the future, advancements in precision apiculture should promote conducting experiments that gather reliable information, resulting in extensive databases accessible to the research community. With sensor systems capable of conducting reliable and stable data collection over a sufficiently extended period (exceeding two years), the generalization of the seasonality of bee colony data would be more robust and reliable, thereby enhancing the predictive capacity of statistical models. This would allow researchers to develop and implement additional predictive models, contributing to the effective management of big data in real time. In addition, the field of precision beekeeping stands to benefit from investigations aimed at establishing the correlation between sensor quality and the precision of predictions produced by diverse models. Through the implementation of dual- or multi-sensor methodologies, such studies would offer the potential to discern whether a direct association exists between sensor quality (including its associated costs) and prediction effectiveness. These endeavors could empower beekeepers in making well-informed decisions regarding the adoption of sensing systems tailored to their apiary needs.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

M. Carmen Robustillo: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Lizbeth Naranjo:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Software, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **M. Isabel Parra:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Supervision, Resources, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Carlos J. Pérez:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The used data have been downloaded from <https://we4bee.org/>.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary material related to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compag.2024.109390>.

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